

Performance of rice mutants in different seasons

N. Kulkarni, A. Gangaram, and M. Kashikar, Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Samba Mahsuri, a quality rice variety grown in Andhra Pradesh, India, has a 150-d duration. Through mutation breeding, early mutants of 120-140 d duration were spotted. We evaluated 12 of them in the M5 (monsoon 1994), M6 (winter 1994-95), and M7 (monsoon 1995) generations along with their parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design in a 7.2-m² plot with three replications and 15- × 15-cm spacing. The low temperature in the monsoon season ranged from 22.3 to 24.4 °C during the 2 mo of seedling and vegetative growth. During the corresponding period in the winter, the low temperature was 9.2-15.5 °C, resulting in a 19 d longer flowering duration (Table 1).

Individual mutants behaved differently in the two seasons, with flowering delayed from 5.0 to 30.5 d in the winter compared with the monsoon season. Among these, M12 and M41

showed the least delay in flowering (5.0 and 11.5 d, respectively).

Grain yield in the winter was more than during the monsoon season because of the dry weather and prolonged duration. The pooled analysis of variance (data not shown) indicated that seasonal effects were significant (Table 2). Differences among the mutants and their interactions with seasons were also significant. Mutants suitable for one or both seasons were identified: M34, M41, and M47 for the monsoon season; M9, M16, and M22 for the winter; and M16 and M22 for both seasons. ■

Table 1. Mean values for days to flowering and grain yield of different rice mutants and their parent varieties.

Mutant	Days to 50% flowering					Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				
	Monsoon		Mean	Winter		Monsoon		Mean	Winter	
	1994	1995		1994-95	Difference	1994	1995		1994-95	Difference
M7	109	112	110.5	129	18.5	4.8	5.3	5.1	5.6	0.5
M8	100	102	101.0	127	26.0	6.5	3.4	5.0	6.8	1.8
M9	91	94	92.5	123	30.5	5.1	4.7	4.9	9.1	4.2
M11	97	105	101.0	123	22.0	4.0	4.7	4.4	8.4	4.0
M12	110	106	108.0	113	5.0	4.5	4.6	4.6	2.8	-1.8
M14	107	108	107.5	125	17.5	5.3	5.1	5.2	78.4	2.2
M16	99	101	100.0	125	25.0	6.2	3.4	4.8	9.7	4.9
M22	105	108	106.5	127	20.5	5.8	5.2	5.5	11.1	5.6
M34	100	102	101.0	114	13.0	6.2	5.2	5.7	5.8	0.1
M41	105	102	103.5	115	11.5	6.9	5.3	6.1	6.6	0.5
M47	114	110	112.0	140	28.0	6.6	4.4	5.5	2.6	-2.9
Samba-Mahsuri (check)	120	122	121.0	140	19.0	4.9	5.1	5.0	7.5	2.5
Mean	105	106	105.5	125	19.5	5.6	4.7	5.2	6.9	1.8
SE±	0.4	0.3	-	0.4	-	0.2	0.3	-	0.4	-

Table 2. Mean sum of squares from pooled ANOVA.

Source	df	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Mutant	11	433.0** ^a	694.0**
Season	2	2444.5**	2335.0**
Mutant × season	22	29.2**	266.0**
Error	42	1.1	94.5
s ² Mutant		44.9	52.0
s ² Season		67.1	64.9
s ² Mutant × season		9.3	43.9

^a** = significant at the 0.01 level.

Using anther culture to generate fertile, doubled-haploid interspecific progeny

M. P. Jones, S. Mande, A. Daleba, and H. Sehi, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), 01 BP 2551, Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire, West Africa

Anther culture enables the rapid genetic fixation of progeny from crosses. In the context of wide crosses, anther culture can also provide fertile doubled haploid progeny with fixed introgressions that might otherwise

disappear in the course of an extended series of backcrosses. We are using anther culture and embryo rescue techniques to accelerate and improve the efficiency of the wide *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* hybridization program at WARDA. The program was expanded to classify representative japonica, indica, and *O. glaberrima* genotypes and their F₁ and F₂ progeny for suitability for anther culture.

We carried out anther cultures for 10 parental lines and the progeny of 55 japonica/japonica, japonica/indica, and *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* crosses.

Main stem boots were collected when flag leaves were exerted 4-8 cm. Panicles were disinfected and cold pre-treated at 8 °C for 10-20 d depending on varietal type. Anthers were incubated in the dark at 25±1 °C in modified N6 medium. Calli obtained were regenerated in Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with a 16-h photoperiod at 25 °C. Plantlet regeneration was induced with the base MS salts and 3 mg thiamine-HCl L⁻¹, 1 mg IAA L⁻¹, 4 mg GA₃ L⁻¹, and 2% (w/v) sucrose.

Response to callus induction and green plantlet regeneration depended